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*Asia Khilkovska***EDUCATION IN EMERGENCIES**

The paper summarizes unique experience of «People's Ukrainian Academy» gained over the years of a full-scale invasion. A small private education institution situated in Kharkiv, heavily affected by military operations, has never stopped working, supported its students and staff, and provided a high-quality training to education seekers. The paper explains what pre-requisites helped the university to withstand at the beginning of the war and looks into a PUA's complex strategy employed in wartime. Several lines of effort are outlined in the article.

Firstly, the paper highlights the importance of the course content quality and reliability of the platform that hosts online courses and ensures Teacher-Student interaction. Secondly, it is shown how a teacher's role has changed in the context of war. New communication styles established within academic communities are explicated. Special attention in the article is paid to the concept of individual and institutional resilience and factors boosting it. Finally, the paper explains the way how volunteering initiatives prove to be more than just serving the public in times of trouble. Volunteering is seen as a powerful tool for bringing people together by encouraging community dialogue, fostering solidarity and a shared sense of purpose. In conclusion, the author emphasizes that continuing formal education in wartime manifests the ability of human spirit to thrive against the odds, therefore, fuels hope and strength people need to endure trials.

Key words: resilience, adaptability, communication, positive reinforcement, human-centred approach, volunteering initiatives.

Хільковська Ася Олександрівна. Освіта в умовах надзвичайної ситуації.

У статті здійснена спроба узагальнити досвід «Народної української академії», накопичений за роки повномасштабної агресії проти України. Невеликий за розміром навчальний заклад, розташований у Харкові, місті, що зазнало важких руйнувань, не припиняв працювати, підтримувати своїх студентів та педагогічний склад, здійснювати якісну підготовку здобувачів освіти всіх рівнів. Стаття окремо вказує на передумови, що дозволили університету вистояти і зберегтися після початку війни, та аналізує комплексну стратегію, яка реалізується закладом у воєнний час, на думку автора, складається з декількох напрямів діяльності.

По-перше, у статті підкреслюється необхідність удосконалення змісту дистанційних курсів, їх актуалізації, та підвищення надійності платформ, що забезпечують взаємодію вчителя та студента в онлайн просторі. По-друге, показано, як змінилася роль вчителя/викладача у контексті війни. Визначений новий стиль комунікації, прийнятий академічними спільнотами у нових умовах. Особливу увагу приділено поняттям індивідуальної та інституційної стійкості та факторам, що сприяють її укріпленню. Автор стверджує, що волонтерські ініціативи університету під час війни вирішують завдання більші, ніж допомога громаді у кризові часи, волонтерська діяльність є ще одним фактором, що формує стійкість, об'єднує людей, сприяє діалогу в громаді та усвідомленню спільної цілі. У підсумку стаття зазначає, що продовження освіти під час війни демонструє здатність людського духу досягати успіху попри все, а тому живить надію та дає сили долати труднощі.

Ключові слова: стійкість, адаптивність, комунікація, позитивна підтримка, людино-центричний підхід, волонтерські ініціативи.

Having lived through the three years of a full-scale war, Ukrainian universities did prove that education in wartime IS possible. «People's Ukrainian Academy» – a relatively small private education institution situated in Kharkiv, which had to go online in March 2022 – has accumulated unique experience of supporting its students and staff and, moreover, of providing a high-quality training at the time of war [1].

PUA had several prerequisites for survival in emergency, among which were: an established e-learning platform Moodle with a range of online courses, some experience of online teaching/learning obtained over the months of the global pandemic and a range of digital tools mastered by the teachers lately. We should also mention the factors that proved to be as important if not more: mental resilience of the team, social connection between people, and adaptability, which are crucial in challenging situations.

However, the war on an unprecedented scale led to unprecedented challenges to people, families, and institutions, and surprisingly, getting back to a routine of everyday classes, lectures, home tasks, projects, and even extra-curricular activities in March 2022, though seemed insane, turned out to be a life-saving decision. Soon it became evident that at this time it was not simply a transition from offline to online, it was a complex strategy involving several directions of effort: improving online interaction between

teachers and students to compensate for not having any face-to-face communication; ensuring the quality and topicality of the course content; maintaining standards, but at the same time easing rules and deadlines so that students in difficult circumstances or having no Internet connection could do course tasks in Moodle at their own pace; ensuring instant communication in various messengers within academic communities to create a common space for mutual support so as to have actual information about where every community member is and what their situation is at any moment. Communication in messengers between teachers and students, between teaching and administrative staff has also undergone a serious transformation, it was no longer asking/answering course-related questions, giving feedback, comments or clarification, announcing results, instead, it became a way to feel belongingness and togetherness, academic chats allowed information that had never been there before: breaking news, warnings, non-related discussions, jokes, mems, videos, anything that was considered helpful to someone at the moment. Instant responses to requests in chats became really crucial, so teachers and managers did their best to react promptly regardless of the time and place. This way a supportive professional network was gradually built.

Under the circumstances of war, the role of the teacher has shifted towards motivating, encouraging and supporting learning efforts of their students [5]. The value of every academic achievement is becoming incomparably greater as it is attained by day-to-day overcoming extraordinary challenges, such as displacement, lack of resources, psychological stresses, and interruptions to learning, so teachers have a hard task to balance between standards and positive reinforcement, assessment and empathy, academic objectivity and a human-centred approach.

Another line of effort for those committed to get through a life-and-death period in the history of our country is cultivating an individual and institutional resilience, the ability to recover after shocks and set-backs being stronger and even more capable than before. Human resilience is innate, though some individuals may be more predisposed to it than others, resilience develops through experiences, supportive environment, institutional culture, and intentional practices. Individuals are more likely

to develop and demonstrate resilience when they can master healthy coping mechanisms and their effort is supported and rewarded by the institution they work for or study in [4].

Providing supportive environment to both students and staff, «People's Ukrainian Academy» has always set ambitious development goals, promoted and fostered «Growth Mindset», not only declaratively, but in a most practical way: helping individuals to see problems as challenges, to exploit every opportunity in the crisis, to «open every door the war unlocked to Ukrainian academics and education-seekers». Among the opportunities seized: a record number of Erasmus mobilities, scholarships from foreign universities, joint international research and education projects, guest lectures by PUA lecturers and guest lectures in PUA, courses taught by affiliated professors, international training for teachers and many more. The academy supported its students who attempted to do courses in two universities simultaneously by designing and providing them with individual learning trajectories, and supported professionals of all ages who saw a chance to get back to a university class and get a second qualification or complete a once unfinished course. This way the university significantly boosts the prospects of its teachers and graduates in post-war times on a globalized labour market.

PUA's institutional resilience stands on the collective ability of its stakeholders to withstand and recover after large-scale shocks, on their coordinating efforts, on extended network of partners committed to support each other in emergencies.

Volunteering initiatives and collective efforts of the university and its stakeholders do not only address immediate needs of endangered individuals and communities, but also lay the groundwork for long-term recovery and resilience, as common activities, especially aimed at helping someone in need, bring people together by encouraging community dialogue, fostering solidarity and a shared sense of purpose [5]. PUA's volunteers deliver humanitarian aid to people affected by the war, support military units protecting Kharkiv, organize charity events.

Continuing education in wartime manifests the ability of human spirit to thrive against the odds, fuels hope and strength necessary to endure trials. Universities in war-affected regions of Ukraine have gained unique experience of living and functioning through the war. «People's Ukrainian

Academy» has elaborated a complex strategy which involves a number of directions, most important of which are: improving quality of online learning/teaching and strengthening reliability of online platforms; establishing a new style of communication within the academic community; cultivating individual and institutional resilience, bringing people together through volunteering initiatives and service to the public.

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